

Spectrum of Histopathological Findings among Autopsy Cases in Coastal Karnataka - A Retrospective Study**Penumudi Hema Raja Sri¹, Prakash H Muddegowda², Prashant B Mahalingashetti³, Jyothi B Lingegowda⁴**¹Postgraduate Student, Department of Pathology, Karwar Institute of Medical Sciences, Karwar, Karnataka²Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Karwar Institute of Medical Sciences, Karwar, Karnataka³Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Karwar Institute of Medical Sciences, Karwar, Karnataka⁴Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, Karwar Institute of Medical Sciences, Karwar, Karnataka

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Abstract:**Background:** Histopathological autopsy study helps in identifying various changes in multiple organs that aid in establishing the cause of death. It also helps in evaluation/ confirmation of antemortem/post mortem changes. This study was done to evaluate the spectrum of histopathological findings and to know the most common cause of death amongst autopsy cases in coastal region in Karnataka.**Materials and methods:** A retrospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, including all organs received for medicolegal autopsy for a period of 12 months, to study the spectrum of histopathological findings and also to determine the most common cause of death among autopsy cases in coastal Karnataka.**Results:** A total of 80 cases meeting inclusion and exclusion criteria were studied. Males were 75% and majority were between 35-50 years of age. Most common cause of death was found to be sudden death of cardiac cause. Most common histopathological finding was coronary atherosclerosis (59.4%) (LCA being most common) in the heart. Congestion and edema (85.9%) in Lungs. Steatohepatitis (63.79%) in Liver. Other organs showed predominantly normal histology.**Conclusion:** We conclude that sudden death due to cardiac event is the most common cause of death and coronary atherosclerosis was the most common histopathological finding observed in the area of coastal Karnataka.**Keywords:** Autopsy, sudden death, atherosclerosis, histopathological findings.

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Introduction

Histopathological autopsy study helps in identifying various changes in multiple organs that aid in establishing the cause of death. It also helps in evaluation/ confirmation of antemortem/post mortem changes.[1] Medico-legal autopsy is usually requested in cases of sudden, suspicious, obscure, unnatural, litigious or criminal deaths.[2] Data from National crime records bureau 2019, reveals the incidence of sudden death (SD) in India to be 11.5% and the majority are expected to be due to cardiovascular events.[3,4,5] In our country, as per 2021 WHO data, top causes of death include Ischemic heart disease (IHD), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, stroke and diarrheal diseases.[6] Sudden Cardiac Death (SCD) is frequently found in older age groups and accounts for 45 to

50% of SD. Major causes of SCD is IHD secondary to Atherosclerosis.[7] This study was done to evaluate the spectrum of histopathological findings amongst autopsy cases in coastal region in Karnataka.

Aims and Objectives:

1. To describe the spectrum of histopathological findings related or unrelated to the cause of death among autopsy cases.
2. To determine the most common cause of death among autopsy cases in the area of coastal Karnataka.

Materials and Methods

After obtaining approval from the institutional ethics committee, a retrospective and descriptive observational study was conducted for 12 months from July 2023 to June 2024 in the Department of Pathology at Karwar Institute of Medical Sciences.

Inclusion criteria:

Medicolegal autopsy specimens sent in formalin received in the Department of Pathology from the Department of Forensic Medicine and other health care centers.

Exclusion criteria: Medicolegal autopsy specimens not sent in formalin for histopathological evaluation to the department.

All the autopsy request forms, formalin-fixed gross specimens received during the study period along with Hematoxylin and eosin stained glass slides were retrieved and re-examined. The clinical data like age, gender, cause of death, and microscopy findings were noted.

Statistical analysis: The data collected in Microsoft excel was analyzed statistically using descriptive statistics, namely mean, standard deviation, and percentage.

Results

A total of 92 cases were received for histopathological examination, amongst which 12 specimens were autolyzed. Based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, study included 80 cases.

Among 80 cases, males were 60 (75%), females were 19 (23.8%) and 1 (1.3%) case of undetermined sex identified. Majority of the victims were in the age group of 35-50 years (32, 40%), followed by 22 (27.5%) in 50-75 years (Table 1).

Most common cause of death was found to be sudden death in 42 (52.8%), followed by poisoning in 12 (15%) of the victims (Table 2).

Table 1: Age distribution of study subjects

S.No	Age group (in years)	Frequency (N=80)	Percentage (%)
1.	< 1 month	1	1.3
2.	1 month - 1 year	2	2.5
3.	1 – 20	2	2.5
4.	20 – 35	19	23.8
5.	35 – 50	32	40.0
6.	50 – 75	22	27.5
7.	> 75	2	2.5
9.	Total	80	100

Table 2: Distribution of victims according to cause of death in the present study

S.No	Cause of Death	Frequency (N=80)	Percentage (%)
1.	Sudden death	42	52.8
2.	Poisoning	12	15.0
3.	Asphyxia	8	10.1
4.	Drowning	5	6.3
5.	RTA	5	6.3
6.	Electrocution	2	2.5
7.	Burns	2	2.5
8.	Snake bite	2	2.5
9.	Bee sting	1	1.3
10.	Jellyfish sting	1	1.3
11.	Total	80	100

The most common organs received were Heart (69, 86.25%), lungs (64, 80%), liver (58, 72.5%), and kidneys (56, 70%). A few other tissues including skin from the ligature mark, burnt area and site of electrical injury also received (Table 3).

Table 3: Various organs received for histopathological examination

Organs received	No. of Specimens (N=80)	Percentage (%)
Lungs	64	80
Heart	69	86.25
Liver	58	72.5
Kidney	56	70
Spleen	10	12.5
Uterus	6	7.5
Cervix	6	7.5
Ovary	6	7.5
Fallopian tubes	6	7.5
Brain	3	3.75
Neck structures	2	2.5
Gall bladder	3	3.75
Stomach	1	1.25
Other tissues	13	16.25
Esophagus	1	1.25
GE junction	1	1.25
Duodenum	1	1.25
Pancreas	1	1.25
Small intestine	1	1.25

More than one lesion was identified in most of the heart specimens.

The common gross pathological findings noted in frequency were coronary atherosclerotic changes (41, 59.4%), old myocardial infarction (11, 15.9%) (Figure 1) followed by ventricular hypertrophy (6, 8.69%) (Figure 2). Amongst 41 cases, showing atherosclerosis, frequency of atherosclerosis was

noted more commonly in the left coronary artery (LCA) (41 cases) followed by left anterior descending artery (LAD) (40 cases). (Table 4). Scar tissue in ventricular wall signifying old myocardial infarction was noted in 11 cases.

Acute MI changes was noted in two cases. Left ventricular hypertrophy was noted in 6 cases and right ventricular hypertrophy in 1 case.

Table 4: Histopathological findings in coronary vessels and aorta

	RCA (%)	LCA (%)	LAD (%)	LCxA (%)	Aorta (%)
Patent	31 (38.8)	28 (35.0)	29 (36.3)	35 (43.8)	43 (62.3)
Atheroma	31 (38.8)	31 (38.8)	33 (41.3)	32 (40.0)	24 (34.8)
Calcified atheroma	7 (8.8)	10 (12.5)	7 (8.8)	2 (2.5)	2 (2.9)

Figure 1: Photomicrograph of myocardium showing old MI with scar (H&E, 10x) and inset showing gross image with pale, fibrosed area at apex.

Figure 2: Gross picture showing LVH

Figure 3: Photomicrograph of myocardium showing neutrophilic infiltration(H&E, 10x)

Figure 4: Photomicrograph of coronary artery showing atheroma-cholesterol crystals and calcification (H&E, 10x)

Figure 5: Photomicrograph of aorta showing Intimal Xanthoma, foamy macrophages in the intima (H&E, 20x)

Histopathology of Lung specimens predominantly showed congestion and edema (55, 85.9%) followed by Tuberculosis and pneumonia (4 cases each). One case showed emphysematous changes. (Table 5). The most common histopathological findings in the liver were Steatohepatitis (37), congestion (5), and Cirrhosis (2), followed by one

case of tuberculosis. Normal histology of the liver was noted in 13 cases. (Table 6). Kidneys showed predominantly congestion. Other findings included three cases of chronic pyelonephritis, one case of chronic glomerulosclerosis, chronic glomerulonephritis was noted. Also, one case of simple renal cyst was noted. (Table 7).

Table 5: Histopathological findings in Lungs

Lesions in Lungs	Frequency (n=64)	Percentage (%)
Congestion and edema	55	85.9
Pneumonia	4	6.25
TB	4	6.25
Focal emphysematous changes	1	1.56

Figure 6: Photomicrograph showing tubercular granuloma in the hilar lymph node of Lung (H&E, 10x)

Figure 7: Photomicrograph showing tubercular granuloma in liver parenchyma (H&E, 10x)

Table 6: Histopathological findings in Liver

Lesions in Liver	Frequency (n=58)	Percentage (%)
Steatohepatitis	37	63.79
Congestion	5	8.62
Cirrhosis	2	3.44
TB	1	1.72
Normal histology	13	22.4

Amongst 10 specimens of spleen received, normal histology was noted predominantly (8, 80%), followed by two cases of congestion.

Skin from the bite site was received only in one case of snake bite and showed non-specific changes like features of resolving inflammatory lesion. Skin bit received from the site of bee sting showed ulcerated epidermis with scab formation. In case of jellyfish sting, skin from the bite site was not

received. Amongst changes due to electrocution, subepidermal separation, epidermal cell nuclear elongation and streaming, and dark staining of epidermal nuclei were identified.

Other organs received like the stomach, duodenum, pancreas, brain, uterus, cervix, ovaries and fallopian tubes showed normal histology. One specimen of small intestine received showed ischemic mucosal injury. (Figure 9)

Table 7: Histopathological findings in Kidney

Lesions in Kidneys	Frequency (n=56)	Percentage (%)
Congestion	22	39.28
Chronic pyelonephritis	3	5.35
Chronic glomerulosclerosis	1	1.78
Chronic glomerulonephritis	1	1.78
Simple renal cyst	1	1.78
Normal histology	28	50.0

Figure 8: Photomicrograph showing atrophied tubules with thyroidisation in chronic pyelonephritis of Kidney (H&E, 20x)

Among 8 cases of asphyxia deaths, two specimens of neck structures were received and both cases showed intact hyoid bone. Skin from the site of the ligature mark was received in one case, which showed features of antemortem injury. One specimen of retroperitoneal mass received and showed tuberculosis in the lymph nodes. External genitalia received in case of undetermined sex, showed penile structure histopathologically.

Figure 9: Photomicrograph of small intestine showing features of ischemic mucosal injury (H&E, 10x)

Discussion

In our study, majority were males 60 (75%), and most common age group of the victims was between 35-50 years 32 (40.0%). In a study conducted by Patel S et al., [8] majority were males 121 (60.0%) and most of the victims were in 21-40 years age group 98 (48.5%).

The most common cause of death in our study was cardiac cause (42, 52.8%). Rao D et al., [9] study also showed similar findings. Heart is the predominantly received organ in our study and showed majorly old and acute MI comprising 13 out of 69 cases. Similarly, in study conducted by Pandey V et al., [10] 65 out of 208 cases showed early and late features of MI. In a study conducted by Singh A et al., [11] 26 out of 108 cases showed features of MI.

Our study found 6 cases of LVH, 1 case of LVH + RVH out of 69 cases. Singh A et al., [11] found 15 cases of LVH, 3 cases of LVH + RVH out of 108 cases. In our study, LCA (41 out of 69) was the most common artery showing atherosclerosis, and calcification noted in 10 cases, followed LAD. Similarly, in study by Pandey V et al., [10] LCA was majorly involved comprising of 31 cases, of with 3 cases showed calcification. Singal P et al., [12] also reported major involvement of LCA (48 out of 108), followed by LAD (19 cases out of 108). Lungs are the next major number of organs received in our study. The most common histopathological lesion identified was pulmonary congestion and edema (55, 85.9%) followed by equal proportions of pneumonia and tuberculosis (4, 6.25%). Similarly, in the study of Dhruw D et al., [13] also identified the most common finding to be Congestion with Pulmonary oedema seen in 352 (74.25%). Pneumonia observed in 32 (6.74%), Tuberculosis in 7, (1.48%). In our study focal emphysema observed in 1 case (1.56%). Similarly, Dhruw D et al., [13] found 3, (0.63%) cases of emphysema in their study. In the study of Prakasam G et al., [14] found most common pathology to be pulmonary edema (34%) followed by congestion

(31%), emphysematous change (13%), pneumonia (10%) and tuberculosis (6%). In contrast to our study, Goswami P R et al., [15] found Pneumonia (33.8%) as the commonest finding followed by emphysema (15.8%) and chronic Granulomatous inflammation Tuberculosis (12.9%).

Steatohepatitis (37, 63.8%) was the most common histopathological finding among liver specimens in our study. Similarly, in a study by Hingway S et al., [16] fatty change (32.8%) was the most common finding. Cirrhosis and tuberculosis identified in 8.62% and 1.72% of cases respectively in our study. Hingway S et al., [16] found Cirrhosis (8.2%) and Tuberculosis (1.1%) in their study. Around 22.4% of normal liver histology identified in our study, similar results observed in a study by Kaushal N et al., [1] of 20%. Among kidney lesions, congestion (37.5%) was the most common histopathological finding followed by chronic pyelonephritis (5.35%), glomerulosclerosis (1.78%), glomerulonephritis (1.78%) and 1.78% of simple renal cyst. Similar results were observed in a study by K RR et al., [17]

Only in one case, the skin tissue received from the site of ligature mark showed features of antemortem injury in our study. In a study conducted by K L S et al., [18] found majority of the received cases showing features of antemortem injury.

Conclusion

The study highlights the various common causes of death and spectrum of histopathological findings in multiple organs of victims of autopsy. The most common findings on histopathology may or may not be related to the cause of death, but the evidence of these lesions in autopsy cases helps to identify the various pathologic processes in multiple organs and to take necessary preventive measures in the form of health care programs, early diagnosis, and treatment.

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